

EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATION STUDY OF GFRP WITH LOCAL FIBRE DEFLECTION UNDER BEARING LOADS

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Introduction

Problem and Motivation

Bearing Test

- GFRP: HP-U400E, 417 g/m², Epoxid resin RIMR135/RIMH1366, approx. 55% FVC
- ASTM D5961/D5961M-17: Single- / Double shear

Simulation

- Implementation of fibre deflection
- Progressive damage behaviour
- Optimisation of damage parameters

Ultimate Bearing Stress and Stress Ratio

Failure Mode after Double Shear Bearing Test

Development of Material Model

- Development of material model with progressive damage behaviour
- Evaluation of main damage parameters
- Optimisation of damage parameters

Comparison of Simulation to Experimental Results

